

Beyond Open Research: Understanding what matters for quality and reliability

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Algorithm: A set of mathematical instructions or rules that, especially if given to a computer, will help to calculate an answer to a problem (in [Cambridge English Dictionary](#))

Artificial Intelligence: A computer program or machine that has the ability to interpret and produce information in a way that seems human, to recognise or create images, to solve problems, and to learn from data supplied to it (see [Cambridge English Dictionary](#))

DORA: The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (see [website](#))

FAIR principles: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability, (more in [Go FAIR](#)), as applied to research data.

h-index: Hirsch's index, abbreviated as h-index, is a number calculated to measure both productivity and research impact by combining the number of publications and the number of citations to these publications (in [Framework of Open and Reproducible Research Training](#)). A researcher with h-index 5 has published 5 journal articles that have each gone on to be cited at least 5 times.

Metadata: Information about data that promotes discovery, structures data objects, and supports the administration and preservation of records (in [Society of American Archivists dictionary](#)). Metadata can include the name of a file, the timestamp showing when it was created, the owner and the file pathway allowing others to find it.

Negative data: Results that are inconclusive or unexpected, either because they contradict the existing literature or because they demonstrate that a hypothesis is incorrect (see [Negative results: the data are the data](#), Texas Tech University).

Open Research: A set of principles and practices that enable research to be freely shared and reused. At Imperial, Open Research enables transparency, equity, accessibility and reliability (in [Open Research](#), Imperial College London).

Research culture: The behaviours, values, expectations, attitudes and norms of our research communities. It influences researchers' career paths and determines the way that research is conducted and communicated. ([Research Culture | Royal Society](#))

Research data: Any information that has been collected, observed, generated or created to validate original research findings. Although usually digital, research data also includes non-digital formats such as laboratory notebooks and diaries (in [What is research data?](#), University of Leeds).

Reliability: How consistently a research method, model or AI method produces stable results. If the same result can be consistently achieved under the same circumstances, the measurement is considered reliable.

Reproducibility: A minimum standard for assessing the value or accuracy of scientific claims based on re-analysing the original methods, data and code (in [Framework of Open and Reproducible Research Training](#)). A reproducible study is one where re-analysis of the same data using the same methods yields the same results.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

The Project set out to:

- Identify the practices and behaviours that matter in the development of a positive research culture that emphasises the public interest in high-quality research.
- Identify the issues and factors that matter in the development of a collaborative, generalisable workflow for research data transparency and scrutiny, particularly as applicable to models and AI in decision-making.
- Identify research software packages that could benefit from Open Research support and possible departmental activities to help enhance research software awareness and skills.
- Start to build an Open Research community of practice, supporting motivated individuals to take ownership of Imperial's research culture.

All activities proposed were carried out as planned:

- Four scoping and co-creation workshops engaging researchers, PTO (professional, technical and operational) staff and members of the public including patients and clinicians. The workshops aimed to identify the challenges of engaging with open data and asked questions about the practical meaning of terms like quality and reliability, particularly in the context of data-based applications such as AI in patient treatment. The workshops then moved to finding solutions to the challenges identified, with participants considering the practical and realistic things that could be done to transform the research culture around research data at Imperial.
- Three semi-structured interviews were conducted with subject matter experts on recognition, incentives and research assessment; open and FAIR data and robustness of research data; reliability of data-based applications in society and decision-making.
- 15 PhD students from 13 Imperial departments were recruited as Research Software Champions (RSC) to raise the profile of research software within their domains. The RSCs carried out departmental surveys and held open discussions and workshops to identify challenges their colleagues were facing in the management of research software. They looked at what could be done to facilitate a culture of good practice in Research Software Engineering and participated in related activities such as contributing to the [podcast episode on Research Software Champions](#). Some RSCs contributed to the four main workshops as participants and note-takers.

All aims set out have been achieved. In some cases, this has culminated in fresh questions to address in future work. For example, the question of what “data scrutiny” looks like, whether there is a common language around it and the premise of whether it is possible to do it in a generalisable way needs to be explored further. It may be more accurately described as “data practice scrutiny”.

KEY OUTCOMES

The key outcomes comprised a series of recommendations:

- Promote uptake of data management plans for the researchers concerned with doing the research and not limited to PIs. This will enhance and complement [the existing Research Office policy](#), and will require infrastructure such as a data repository, widespread training in data management and data quality and funding for expanded capacity in the Research Data Management team.
- Expand the model of patient involvement to engage members of the wider public in the development of data-based tools and applications in healthcare. This will help ensure that the perspectives of a wider group of stakeholders are represented.
- Expand the collaborative approach to developing new policies and standards on openness, transparency of data and research culture, recognising that sustainable solutions follow from a collective effort beyond one institution.
- Co-create a standard for “data peer review” to address the urgent need for practices to scrutinise research data.
- Engage College teams concerned with assessment and reward, including HR, to ensure coherence between the development of responsible practices and recognition of those practices, particularly aspiring to recognise team science. There should be a particular focus on academic promotions.
- The need for sufficient resourcing to make the most of the opportunities that a cohort of RSCs can enable.

The above came out of workshop discussions supplemented by semi-structured interviews and our experience in coordinating the project. They take in the views of researchers at various career stages, PTO staff and members of the public – all with different levels of understanding of the context.

The project supported the production of a podcast series by Peter Schmidt, producer of ‘Code for Thought’. In the series of three episodes, [Peter talked with the project leads, as well as Prof Julie McCann](#), Chair of the Researcher Development Committee, [a selection of the RSCs](#) and with [Dr Jeremy Cohen and Dr Mike Bearpark about the RSC scheme](#). At the fourth workshop, a visual facilitator, Rae Goddard, [produced an illustration of the day](#). This was highly relevant to the discussion on diversifying the research outputs that we recognise and value. The podcast series and graphics provide high-quality, non-textual and lasting outputs.

FINDINGS

The workshop findings result from qualitative analysis of the data collected by the note-takers during the introductory talks and breakout discussions. Each workshop was organised into three sessions.

A digital Microsoft OneNote notebook was created for each session containing the notes from all the breakout groups. The analysis below mirrors the structure and sequence of the workshops.

For each document, there were pre-established topics of analysis (codes), resulting from the specific themes of each session. After a first reading of the notes, new topics were created as they emerged from the group discussion reflected in the notes. The codes were subsequently clustered into themes.

For the purpose of this document, we selected the three themes with more impact in each session (numbered and in *italics*) and for each one of them we present a brief description of the aggregated topics.

Organisation of the workshops' findings:

Workshop - **TITLE**

Aims of the workshop:

Session 1 – Title

Topic statement

1 Themes

Topics:

Session 2 – Title

Topic statement

1 Themes

Topics:

Session 3 – Title

Topic statement

1 Themes

Topics:

Organisation of the interviews' findings:

Interview Title

1. **Key subjects**

- Topics:

Workshops

Workshop 1: CHALLENGES OF TRANSPARENCY, QUALITY AND INTEGRITY IN RESEARCH DATA

11 April 2024, South Kensington Campus

Aims of this workshop:

- Identify why it matters, in research and society, for data to be open, transparent and high-quality
- Identify subject-specific challenges, barriers and opportunities in engaging with Open Data practices at Imperial

Session 1 Fostering a Culture of Open Research, intro. by Professor Ian Walmsley, Provost, Imperial College London

Fostering an open research culture requires us to develop infrastructure and break down silos across the university.

1. *Practices and behaviours to improve research quality*

Collaboration: Encourage collaboration and sharing of practices, experiences, and results at institutional, national and international levels.

Negative results: Promote open access to code, methods and data, and ensure the publication of negative results to prevent bias towards successful outcomes.

Reproducibility: Enhance reproducibility by providing training, allocating resources, developing standards for data and metadata management.

2. *Obstacles to Open Research*

Lack of College infrastructure: The college lacks a solution for storing raw data due to cost challenges, affecting data robustness and reliability, though a college-wide repository is being developed.

Siloed research at Imperial: Different groups lack standardised data structuring, leading to isolated processes and potential risks due to lack of interconnectivity.

Recognition: Participants have mixed experiences with citation and recognition, with some facing work overload and a lack of formal roles for data scientists or curators.

Legislation: Data protection and intellectual property issues create obstacles for data sharing and open research, especially in medical research.

3. *Transparency*

Transparency: Research results should be repeatable and testable, requiring transparent data with proper data dictionaries and metadata.

Peer review: The peer-review system needs to be more transparent and include quality checks, with questions about funding and reviewer selection.

Session 2 Openness and Scrutiny in Data Science, intro. by Chris Gullick, Chief Data and Artificial Intelligence Officer, Ofgem

To improve data openness and scrutiny, we need to recognise the right things and equip researchers to improve transparency at every stage of research.

1. Data challenges

Reliability and bias: Data interpretation is influenced by the collection process and methodologies, requiring careful data treatment and documentation of the data lifecycle to avoid errors.

Importance of metadata: Consistent metadata and uncertainty measurements are essential to address subjectivity and potential errors in data collection and interpretation.

Subject-specific issues concerning null/negative result publishing: Publishing negative results is straightforward in fields with clear protocols like clinical trials, but less clear in fields like computing/electronics where experimentation is more exploratory.

2. Obstacles to Open Research

Bureaucracy: Open research is often viewed as an additional bureaucratic burden, but there is an opportunity to create a supportive institutional framework that may reduce this weight over the lifetime of the research.

Data storage: The lack of infrastructure and the impracticality of a one-size-fits-all policy for data collection methods poses significant barriers to research.

Environmental aspects: The environmental impact of data storage conflicts with the institution's goal of achieving net zero carbon emissions by 2040.

3. Data quality:

Data quality: Chris Gullick identified accuracy, completeness and timeliness as the three main aspects of data quality.

Data peer review: Peer-reviewing data, rather than just methods, is necessary to ensure data quality.

Session 3 Data in Decision-Making and Society, intro. by Dr Hamid Khan, Open Research Manager, Imperial College London

Overcoming challenges in the way data is used in society requires more public engagement and focus on data robustness and AI reliability.

1. Data challenges

Real-time responses: Collecting and managing clean, structured data is not possible in contexts of precarious infrastructures, disease outbreaks, war and political instability.

Data Management Plans (DMP): Awareness of the importance of DMPs varies across domains, but data documentation is essential throughout the data collection and modelling process.

2. ***Practices and behaviours to improve research quality***

Public engagement: The session emphasised the importance of building and collaborating with data providers from Global South countries and working closely with collaborators in real-world situations.

Embracing failure: Innovation requires risk and failure as part of the process, but the current culture does not support failure, which can harm careers and reputations.

Data quality and reproducibility: There is a suggested correlation between data quality and reproducibility, with more reproducible data likely being more reliable

Workshop 2: HOW MUCH CAN WE RELY ON AI IN PATIENT TREATMENT?

9 May 2024, The Invention Rooms, White City Campus

Aims of this workshop:

- Identify public experiences of AI in decision-making, focussing on healthcare.
- Explore public questions, concerns and aspirations about the reliability of AI in decision-making and the data used to build models and AI.
- Provide societal context for the project, helping us understand what the public interest in research culture might look like.

Session 1 Data, models and AI in decision-making, intro. by Marc Boubnovski-Martell, Imperial College London

Concerns about AI's limitations and biases impacting equality, diversity and inclusivity (EDI) can be balanced against its potential for personalised healthcare and its role in complementing, rather than replacing, human expertise.

1. ***AI***

AI outlook: Participants' impressions towards AI varied from distrust and fear to profound belief.

Personalisation: The potential of AI for personalised treatment was a significant and widely agreed-upon benefit in healthcare, helping to counter the perception of AI as dehumanising.

AI as a tool: Defining AI as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human jobs was seen as a balanced and reassuring perspective.

2. ***Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity (EDI)***

AI EDI limitations: The limitations of AI for elderly, non-English speakers, disabled and neurodivergent people were discussed in-depth.

Digital poverty: Participants highlighted challenges in harnessing AI benefits due to issues of language (preponderance of English) and lack of accurate data regarding minority groups or marginalised communities.

3. ***Bias***

AI biases: Concerns were raised about data, algorithmic and computational biases, particularly regarding geographical, linguistic, ethnic diversity and inclusion.

Session 2 What makes an AI trustworthy? intro. by Dr Zeynep Engin, Data for Policy CIC / University College London

Reliable AI complements human decision-making and enhances patient understanding; however, embedding trustworthiness requires better understanding and balanced narratives about AI, along with robust policies and oversight to ensure its ethical and secure use.

1. Trustworthiness

Understanding AI: There was a consensus on the need for a better understanding of AI to build trust, highlighting the importance of knowledge exchange between experts and the public.

(Re)framing AI: Participants noted the focus on AI's negative impacts and called for more success stories to balance the narrative and rebuild trust in decision-makers.

2. AI

AI higher standards: AI is held to a higher standard than doctors, but it should complement, not replace, human decision-making in healthcare.

AI aids in explaining the course of treatment: AI can enhance patient understanding by providing detailed explanations of treatment decisions, complementing brief clinician visits.

3. Develop policies

Surveilling AI: Ensuring AI systems operate within legal frameworks and protect personal data is crucial, with explicit quality control and human oversight.

Session 3 Challenges of reliability in AI, intro. by Dr Raquel Iniesta, King's College London

Building trustworthy and reliable AI requires broad public involvement, continuous feedback, accountability and transparent communication to ensure AI complements human decision-making and empowers patients.

1. Public Involvement

Broader public involvement: Public involvement should encompass the entire community to enrich the understanding of AI, with a focus on local engagement.

Types of contribution: Public data helps train AI models and continuous patient feedback is essential for assessing and improving model performance over time.

Education for AI: To address AI opacity, there were proposals to include AI education in school curricula, promoting critical thinking and awareness of data privacy and quality from a young age.

2. *Reliability*

Model peer review: At a technological level, reliability depends on the quality of the information provided and the accuracy of the model, making it necessary to peer review and test the robustness of the model

Accountability: Confidence and reliability in AI for patient treatment require mutual trust between doctor and patient to overcome a perceived lack of accountability, which should be addressed through regulatory measures regarding the use of AI.

3. *Transparency*

AI disclosure: Transparent decision-making between doctors and patients about AI usage fosters understandability of AI.

Patients' agency: Awareness and understanding of AI in treatment empower patients, enhancing their engagement and agency in the process.

Workshop 3: DEVELOPING A RESPONSIBLE APPROACH TO DATA IN SOCIETY

5 June 2024, The Invention Rooms, White City Campus

Aims of this workshop:

- Co-creating practical and meaningful solutions to the challenges identified in the previous workshops, to promote data transparency, quality and integrity
- Considering when and how the reliability of data-based applications can be scrutinised before they are used in decision-making, eg. models and AI in patient treatment

Session 1 Making Data FAIR, intro. by Dr Sofia Fernandes, University of Warwick

Data protection and standardisation, along with promoting open access and incentivising FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data, are crucial for sustainable and effective data sharing across domains, researchers and society.

1. *Standards*

Data protection and standardisation: Robust training for data protection officers and standardisation of data logbooks are essential, with challenges arising from inconsistent knowledge organisation and classification systems across regions and disciplines, necessitating customisation for specific sub-domains.

2. *Interoperability*

Data sharing infrastructure: The lack of a standardised method for sharing data across organisations is a significant challenge, highlighting the need for a common infrastructure that accommodates various access methods, legal constraints and long-term sustainability.

Global standards and interoperability: There is a need for global or national standards to ensure interoperability across databases and research domains, requiring data cleaning and integration to meet these standards.

3. *Sustainability*

Research access: Open access to research data is crucial, with differing views on whether it should always be free. Nonetheless, there is a consensus that science benefits from freely shared data.

Incentivising FAIR research: The costs and efforts required to implement FAIR principles are not adequately supported or incentivised, necessitating robust funding and recognition to promote these practices.

Session 2 Scrutinising Data Quality, intro. by Dr Fiona Booth, University of Bristol

Reliable and ethical research practices, such as open methods for data collection and cleaning, open datasets and independent auditing, enhance data quality and transparency, fostering a research culture of trustworthiness, accountability and integrity.

1. *Data quality*

Data transparency and quality control: Transparency in research data is crucial, but it must be accompanied by rigorous quality checks.

Data management and access: Effective data management practices are essential for ensuring data quality and reproducibility, with structured data handling approaches improving research outcomes.

2. *Data challenges*

Risks and mistakes for data quality: Improving data quality while balancing ethical concerns requires an environment where mistakes can be openly acknowledged, along with independent auditing and oversight to ensure research integrity and public trust.

Challenges of data security: Concerns about data security and its impact on public trust highlight the growing anxiety over how personal data is handled.

AI ethics: The responsible use of AI in research necessitates constant oversight due to the ethical implications and reliance on AI, as emphasised by participants.

3. *Research culture*

Patient trust in clinical trials: There is a significant gap in understanding and trust among patients regarding clinical trials, highlighting the need for better engagement and involvement to incorporate trustworthiness.

Scrutiny and accountability: More scrutiny and accountability in research processes are needed, with reforms to peer-review mechanisms to ensure unbiased quality assessments.

Research culture and integrity: The culture within research institutions is crucial for maintaining integrity, emphasising the need to foster the right cultural environment for ethical research practices.

Session 3 Asking the right questions about reliability, intro. by Jennifer Ding, Alan Turing Institute

Building trust and ensuring research relevance requires engaging the public continuously; better-informed communities contribute to ensure AI reliability and transparency by asking the right questions regarding issues such as data provenance.

1. Reliability and integrity

Ask questions: Data reliability and integrity should be addressed proactively, by continuously asking questions, such as: Where does the data come from?

Reliable data: to be reliable, data must be 1) thorough and nuanced, 2) checked for sampling biases (considering that different groups have different response rates, for instance) and 3) continuously updated.

2. Collaboration

Public trust: Involving the public in decision-making processes, especially in areas like health and urban planning, is crucial for building trust, with early patient engagement being key.

Continuous engagement with the community: Continuous engagement is necessary to adapt to the changing needs and priorities of the community, ensuring research remains relevant and beneficial.

3. AI

AI reliability and scrutiny: The reliability of AI models should be continuously scrutinised with independent governance to ensure they reflect public needs and empower informed choices.

Transparency in AI: Understanding data sources and ensuring AI models are transparent and accountable, with continuous validity checks, is crucial, as the quality of AI models depends heavily on the quality of data collected.

Workshop 4: WHAT MATTERS? RECOGNISING AND INCENTIVISING QUALITY AND RELIABILITY

11 July 2024, South Kensington Campus

Aims of this workshop:

- Identify the links between Open Research, quality and reliability on one hand, and recognition and incentives on the other
- Prioritise the practices and behaviours that Imperial researchers and staff think matter for good-quality, reliable research
- Identify the systems, processes and infrastructure that can help foster "excellence" (in research) as an Imperial value and move Imperial beyond publish-or-perish culture.

Session 1 DORA – Recognition, Incentives and Assessment, intro. by Dr Kim Huijpen, Universities of the Netherlands

To enhance research culture, we need to overcome resistance to change by addressing disparities in academic rewards, training on new assessment models and non-traditional research outputs and recognising the value of public engagement.

1. *Research culture*

Mismatch in academic rewards: There is a disparity in academia between what is deemed important and what is rewarded, with narrow indicators like the h-index often misused, highlighting the need to prioritise quality over journal-based metrics.

Training on new assessment models: Better training is needed in evaluating [narrative CVs](#) and EDI statements, with more guidance required from funding bodies and institutions to ensure fair and effective assessments.

2. *Incentives and recognition*

Diversifying academic careers: There is a strong emphasis on diversifying academic career paths to move beyond a one-size-fits-all model, focussing on individual strengths like teaching, research or patient care.

Diversifying research outputs: Concerns were raised about assessing research outputs that are not journal articles, such as software, with calls for more appropriate evaluation methods.

Resistance to change: The challenges of moving away from traditional metrics like the REF [Research Excellence Framework] were discussed, with resistance to change in many institutions being an obstacle to implementing new assessment models.

3. *Enhance practices*

International collaboration: The importance of international alignment on research assessment reforms was highlighted to create a common direction, especially for researchers moving between countries.

Career progression and inclusion: Systemic issues in academia were discussed, particularly how traditional structures hinder the recognition and inclusion of diverse talents, including PTO staff and early-career researchers.

Recognition of public engagement: The importance of public engagement in research was debated, with questions about how to measure its impact and value it in academic assessments.

Session 2 What Matters for Quality and Reliability? intro. by Dr Alexandra Freeman, Octopus

Promoting quality and reliability in (open) research involves supporting the publication of negative results, focussing on methodology and analysis, distinguishing between findings and primary research records and addressing the challenges of peer review.

1. *Open Research*

Shift in research evaluation: The idea of moving away from the "publish or perish" culture towards a system that recognises a broader range of contributions, including methods and data sharing, was discussed as a future goal.

Support for negative results: Participants discussed the importance of publishing negative results to prevent unnecessary duplication of efforts and to enhance the robustness of scientific findings.

Beyond results: Need to focus on the methodology and analysis stages of research, rather than just the final results/outputs, to ensure quality and reliability.

2. *Practices and behaviours to improve research quality*

Critique of ‘good stories’: The focus on publication output and citations can undermine rigorous research processes, promoting appealing stories over sound science.

Octopus - research process: There is a need to distinguish between disseminating findings and maintaining a primary research record, with [Octopus](#) encouraging the publication and peer review of every step in the research process to reflect a more accurate picture of scientific work.

3. *Peer review*

Challenges of peer review: While peer review is essential, the current system is flawed due to a lack of incentives and concerns about its impact on early-career researchers, with open peer review being intimidating for those who fear repercussions from critiquing senior scientists.

Session 3 What is “Excellence” and Can We Measure It? intro. by Professor Stephen Curry, Imperial College London

Excellence is a multifaceted concept that should be measured holistically by integrating processes and outputs, promoting diversity and equity, and adjusting assessment frameworks to encourage risk-taking and learning from failure.

1. *Excellence*

Institutional culture: Institutions should foster a culture that supports holistic excellence, including better career development, incentives for collaboration and a commitment to research integrity.

Diversity and equity: Excellence should involve recruiting from diverse talent pools, ensuring freedom from bullying and harassment and providing better support for researchers with care giving responsibilities.

2. *Assessment*

REF 2029 adjustments: The planned changes to the REF 2029 aim to reshape incentives by adjusting the weight of outputs from 60% to 50%, rethinking what should be recognised and rewarded.

Encouraging risk-taking: Participants appreciated the recognition of risk-taking as a component of good science, alongside learning from failure and publishing null results.

3. *Metrics*

Challenges with metrics: There is concern over the use of metrics to measure excellence, as they might create perverse incentives and overlook important but less quantifiable aspects like research culture and integrity.

Interviews

Recognition, incentives and research assessment, 9 July 2024

Interview with Elizabeth Gadd, Head of Research Culture, Loughborough University

1. Challenges in developing an Open Research Culture

- Defining open research: The challenge lies in the difficulty of defining what constitutes open research, particularly given that it has evolved into an umbrella term encompassing a rapidly growing number of research practices.
- Integration with broader research culture: Open research needs to find its place within the broader research culture, including research integrity and assessment.
- Incentives and assessment: Assessing and incentivising open research without overwhelming researchers is crucial.

2. Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

- Formation and goals: CoARA aims to reform research assessment to promote responsible practices.
- Commitments: CoARA focus on avoiding poor use of publication indicators, evaluating a broader range of outputs and moving towards qualitative assessments.

3. Reforming research assessment

- Importance of qualitative assessment: Emphasising qualitative over quantitative assessment to better capture the value of research is necessary, though both types of analysis are required for responsible research assessment.
- Standards: Research must be open by default, and standards must be clearly defined at the national level; there is a shift from discipline-based standards to adherence to institutional standards regarding open research practices.

4. Team Science and individual recognition

- Balancing individual and team contributions: Recognising the importance of team-based research while also assessing individual contributions may present some challenges, as universities typically recruit individuals rather than entire teams.
- Narrative CVs: The use of narrative CVs may contribute to overcome assessment obstacles by capturing a broader range of contributions and achievements.

5. Future directions and recommendations

- Peer review: To promote formative forms of peer reviewing outputs will improve research quality.
- Open Access to Open Research: Transparency and accountability benefit from an open access to data regarding open research practices.

Interview with Prof Anne ter Wal, Prof David Colling, Ian McArdle and Wayne Peters, Imperial College London

1. Challenges in data transparency

- Confidentiality and sensitivity: Different disciplines, particularly social sciences and business, encounter challenges in sharing data. However, social sciences benefit from advanced repositories like UK Data Services that offer tiered access to data; the Imperial data repository will also provide controlled dataset access.
- Awareness and compliance: It is essential to ensure awareness and adherence to existing data management policies and funder requirements throughout the entire research lifecycle. Transparency regarding the methods of data collection, data sharing practices, and consent permissions will facilitate sharing data while safeguarding legal and ethical considerations.
- Technical infrastructure: The importance of having the right technical infrastructure to support data sharing, especially for sensitive data.
- Support and guidance: Researchers require more support and clearer guidance to adhere to best practices in data management and sharing.

2. Benefits of data transparency

- Increased citations and collaborations: Sharing data can lead to more citations and collaborations.
- Training opportunities: Open data provides valuable training opportunities for doctoral students and junior researchers.
- Preventing fraud: While open data can help prevent academic fraud, and some scientific journals refuse papers that do not provide the open access to the dataset, it is not a foolproof solution, as demonstrated by the case of Francesca Gino¹

3. Negative data and pre-registration

- Challenges with negative data: Although there has been progress with journals that publish negative or null results, this is still not a common practice. While pre-registration may address this issue, its applicability may vary in certain areas.
- Domain-specific solutions: From social sciences to physical sciences research, pre-registration may not universally apply; it is essential to develop domain specific approaches for data sharing.

4. Peer review of data

- Feasibility and implementation: There are challenges and potential benefits of implementing peer review for data, including the need for transparency in data quality checks. Who is doing it and how is it going to be done? Is it just about making sure that the file opens or reviewing a sample of the data? Is the review technical or scientific?
- Two-stage peer review process: A model for peer reviewing in 2 stages was presented, focusing on both 1) the research design and 2) the data analysis, interpretation and conclusions.

¹ See [Embattled Harvard honesty professor accused of plagiarism | Science | AAAS](#) [accessed 11/11/2024].

Interview with Prof Caroline Jay, University of Manchester

1. AI in decision-making

- Definition and scope: AI is a broad term encompassing various technologies, including machine learning and symbolic AI. It is often used for prediction and classification.
- Explainable AI: Importance of developing AI that is understandable and explainable, especially in healthcare.

2. Reliability in AI

- Consistency in the results: Reliability means that given a particular input, it is expected either the same or a very similar output over time.
- Challenges: The main challenge in machine learning is the quality of training data. Issues like population representation and biases in data affect reliability.

3. Understanding and addressing bias

- Public involvement in AI development: Engaging the public early in the development process is crucial to understand their perspectives and ensure the technology meets their needs.
- Workshops: Public understanding of bias in training data is good, but more education on how AI works is needed.

4. Openness and transparency

- Open Research practices: Making data and code open by default is beneficial but challenging in practice, requiring substantial financial and human resources. One of the main issues is identifiability.
- Sharing medical data: While protecting individuals is crucial, much of the current protection focuses on safeguarding institutions and researchers from errors or inadvertent disclosures, rather than prioritising the interests of patients and the public.

5. Incentivising openness

- Funding and recognition: Need for funding and recognition of the time and effort required to make research open.
- Institutional support: Universities can support open research through fellowships, awards and promotion criteria.

6. Key actions for institutions

- Promotion criteria: Including open research practices in promotion criteria can incentivise researchers to adopt best practices in Open Research.
- Cultural change: Creating a culture that values openness and transparency.

Methodology

Our findings stem not only from the content of the workshops and interviews but from the fact of having had them and the way they were organised.

- Mapping exercise to form the project leadership team ensured diverse representation from across faculties, departments, professional services, functional areas and career stages.
- Engagement with senior leadership across faculties and departments, and from the ground up with staff and researcher networks and internal communications, ensured widespread awareness of the project and horizontal, vertical and possibly diagonal dissemination of workshop opportunities.
- Inclusion of the general public and clinicians as well as patients in Workshops 2 and 3 exemplified a progressive model of engagement. The added input of experts allowed for discussion of the context of challenges and feasibility of proposed solutions. Involving public participants who were not patients posed an important challenge in identifying the key points of public interest where those with questions and concerns ought to be involved in the scoping and co-creation processes.
- Multi-faceted engagement types: expression-of-interest form – cascaded down from faculties and departments or shared directly with researcher and staff networks; personal invitations to individuals; second-order distribution to colleagues and personal contacts of project team members; newsletters, events and mailing lists.
- Personal conversations with colleagues ensured a wider representation of researchers and staff beyond those who would ordinarily have an existing interest in discussions of Open Research and research culture. Every workshop had participants who came in with little to no prior understanding of or engagement with the issues at hand.
- The collection and analysis of the data also brings an element of methodological innovation. Breakout discussions facilitated a more granular and nuanced response from participants, which would not have been achieved through surveys. Note-taking during the sessions made possible a mixed methodology for the qualitative analysis of the data, integrating focus group and grounded theory approaches, i.e. a top-bottom and a bottom-up analytical methodology. During data processing, it was possible both to address previously established subjects and to identify unforeseen themes that emerged from the coding of the notes using NVIVO, a software for qualitative textual analysis.